

Ethical Leadership and Work Engagement of Mobile Telecommunication Firms in Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT: This paper empirically examined the association of ethical leadership and work engagement of Mobile Telecommunication Firms in Port Harcourt. From a population of six hundred employees, a sample size of two hundred and forty was drawn based on which questionnaire were distributed and retrieved. The demographic and univariate data were presented with descriptive statistics and hypotheses were tested using the t-test and multiple regression analysis. The result showed a positive relationship between dimensions of ethical leadership and measures of work engagement. The study concluded that ethical leadership is not only good for the leaders' reputation, but is also a contagious practice that is capable of stimulating positive workplace value and practices among workers. The study however recommended among others that: (1) leaders should endeavor to treat their followers with fairness and justice (2) leaders should be responsible enough to recognize that their actions or inactions have effect for the future of the organization and that (3) leaders should carry themselves in a transparent manner as against having their actions shrouded in secrecy

KEYWORDS: ethical, leadership, employee, engagement, mobile, telecommunication

Introduction

Engagement is a construct naturally subsumed within the increasingly popular domains of positive psychology and positive organizational behavior, which aim to enhance employees' positive experiences of work (Shekari 2015). Employee engagement is a desirable condition, has an organizational purpose, and connotes involvement, commitment, passion, enthusiasm, focused effort, and energy so it has both attitudinal and behavioral components (Mills 2012). Today's organizations are indisputably on the search for ways of gaining and sustaining competitive advantage in the face of the dynamic and volatile business milieu they are operating; and of all the resources of business, the contribution of human resources in this direction is not questionable (Chaudhary, Rangnecker and Barua 2012). One way through which employee's performance can improve is through engagement to work. In recent past, the construct of employee engagement has received unprecedented attention as a key determinant of several positive organizational outcomes (Macey, Schneider, Barbera and Young 2009; Bates 2004; Bakker, Demerouti, and Brummelhuis 2012; Baumruk 2004; Markos and Sridevi 2010; Harter, Schmidt and Hayes 2002; Richman 2006).

Employee engagement is an active, positive work-related state that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli et al. 2006). It is also an independent, persistent and pervasive motivational psychological state that accompanies the behavioral investment of personal energy (Schaufeli and Bakker 2010). And it is mostly about passion, commitment, and the willingness to invest oneself and expend one's discretionary effort to help the employer succeed (Madu, Asawo and Gabriel 2017). Engagement like its related constructs is exhibited in response to other antecedents that may arise from other parts of the organization; and one of such parts could be the leadership. Leadership is simply the process of influencing others in a desired direction and it remains a major determinant of the direction an organization may go.

Brown and Mitchel (2010) contend that within a work environment, leaders set the tone for organizational goals and behavior and leaders are often in a position to control many outcomes that affect employees, and what leaders incentivize communicates what they value and motivates employees to act in ways to achieve such rewards. It is not surprising, then, that employees rely on their leaders for guidance when faced with ethical questions or problems (Treviño 1986). Research supports this contention, and shows that employees conform to the ethical values of their leaders

(Schminke, Wells, Peyrefitte, & Sabora 2002). Furthermore, leaders who are perceived as ethically positive influence productive employee work behavior (Mayer, Kuenzi, Greenbaum, Bardes, & Salvador 2009) and negatively influence counterproductive work behavior (Brown & Treviño 2006b; Mayer et al. 2009).

Work engagement is unarguably one of these productive work behaviours; and identifying the situations that foster it is vital for the sustainability and growth of organisations (Bakker and Demerouti 2008; Den Hartog and Belschak 2012; Tims et al. 2011). Several scholars have search for work engagement through other lenses. For example, Chaudharry et al. (2012) looked at it from the perspective of occupational self-efficacy, Saks (2006) studied employee engagement through job characteristics, perceived organizational support, supervisor support, rewards and recognition, procedural justice and distributive justice. Madu et al. (2017) looked at it from the view of work environment as predictor; while Engelbrecht, Heine and Mahembe (2017) studied engagement as a consequence of integrity, ethical leadership and trust. Similarly, ethical leadership has been studied as a predictor of employee performance and in one instance with employee engagement as mediator (Resick et al. 2006; Walumbwa et al. 2009; Zehir & Erdogan 2011; Sabir et al. 2012), there is however a paucity of research that have studied ethical leadership as a predictor of employee engagement, especially in the Nigeria context. It is on this backdrop that our point of departure is rooted to look at ethical leadership as a predictor of employee engagement of manufacturing companies in Nigeria; especially because researchers have begun to treat ethical leadership as a leadership style of its own as against its previous consideration as an accompanying feature of other established leadership styles (see Brown et al. 2005; Kalshoven et al. 2011; Yukl et al. 2011).

Literature

Theoretical Foundation. Social Learning Theory (SLT)

According to social learning theory, for leaders to be seen as ethical leaders by their followers, they must be attractive and credible role models. Social learning theory sheds light on why some individual characteristics of the leader and situational influences are related to followers' perceptions of a leader as an ethical leader. Social learning theory helps to explain why and how ethical leaders influence their followers. Social learning theory (Bandura 1977, 1986) is based on the idea that individuals learn by paying attention to and emulating the attitudes, values and behaviors of attractive and credible models. Most individuals look outside themselves to other individuals for ethical guidance (Kohlberg, 1969; Treviño 1986). Ethical leaders are likely sources of guidance because their attractiveness and credibility as role models draw attention to their modeled behavior. Power and status are two characteristics of models that enhance their attractiveness (Bandura 1986), thus making it more likely that followers will pay attention to ethical leaders' modeled behavior. Brown, Treviño, & Harrison (2005) ground their conceptualization of ethical leadership in social learning theory (Bandura 1977, 1986).

This theory suggests individuals can learn standards of appropriate behavior by observing how role models such as teachers, parents, and leaders behave. Accordingly, ethical leaders "teach" ethical conduct to employees through their own behavior. Ethical leaders are relevant role models because they occupy powerful and visible positions in organizational hierarchies that allow them to capture their follower's attention. They communicate ethical expectations through formal processes (e.g., rewards, policies) and personal example (e.g., interpersonal treatment of others). Effective "ethical" modeling, however, requires more than power and visibility. For social learning of *ethical* behavior to take place, role models must be credible in terms of moral behavior. By treating others fairly, honestly, and considerately, leaders become worthy of emulation by others. Otherwise, followers might ignore a leader whose behavior is inconsistent with his/her ethical pronouncements or who fails to interact with followers in a caring, nurturing style (Yussen & Levy 1975). When followers learn how to be ethical from their leaders, it follows that they will also act ethically and by so doing exhibit positive work behaviours which engagement is one.

Ethical Leadership

Ethics can be defined as the reflection on what is morally right or wrong, good or bad (Pauer-Studer 2010). On the other hand, leadership is “the ability to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute to the effectiveness and success of the organizations of which they are members” (Bass & Bass 2008, 23). The construct-ethical leadership is a product of the amalgam of the two words-ethics and leadership; and it was first introduced by Treviño et al. (2003) and has received a remarkable amount of scholarly interest ever since. Researchers have begun to consider ethical leadership as a separate leadership style in itself rather than focusing only on the ethical elements of other leadership styles (e.g. transformational, authentic and servant leadership) (Brown, et al. 2005, De Hoogh & Den Hartog 2008, 2009; Kanungo 2001; Kalshoven et al. 2011; Yukl et al. 2011).

The fundamentals of ethics according to the Webster dictionary are dealing with what is good and bad, moral duty and moral obligation. This relates closely to how Kanungo (2001) conceptualizes ethical leadership. He takes an altruism approach and addresses ethical leadership as a tension between altruistic and egoistic motives (e.g., Kanungo 2001; Turner, Barling, Epitropaki, Butcher, & Milder 2002). This approach suggests that an ethical leader is driven by a system of accepted beliefs and appropriate judgments rather than self-interest, which is beneficial for followers, organizations and society. This way, Kanungo (2001) and Aronson (2001) emphasize the effect of leader's actions on others as a major concern in ethical leadership. Brown et al. (2005, 120) defined ethical leadership as “the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making”.

The first part of this definition relates to the “moral person” facet of ethical leadership and the second part to the “moral manager” facet (Brown and Trevino 2006). Ethical leadership can be defined as the —demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making (Brown, Treviño, & Harrison 2005, 120). Ethical leadership is a relational concept in the sense that it is constructed in and through social interactions with followers. Furthermore, being an ethical leader is about being both a moral person as well as a moral manager (Treviño, Hartman, & Brown 2000). The moral person‘ part of ethical leadership can be viewed as the personal traits and characteristics of a leader—such as honesty, trustworthiness and integrity—and the moral nature of that leader’s conduct (Treviño & Brown 2005; Treviño et al. 2000).

Dimensions of Ethical Leadership

Resick et al. (2006) empirically distinguished various dimensions of ethical leadership, such as character and integrity, altruism, motivating, encouraging and empowering. Kalshoven et al. (2011) identified similar dimensions, namely fairness, integrity, people orientation, role clarification, ethical guidance and power sharing. In line with these dimensions, Eisenbeiss (2012) identified a humane orientation and a justice orientation of ethical leadership. For the purpose of this work however, the seven dimensions of ethical leadership would be used as follows-

- **People orientation:** This implies the behavior of having true concern for people; a prominent feature in Blake and Mouton’s Managerial Grid. Incidentally, this dimension happens to be one of the most frequently mentioned parts of ethical leadership in Treviño et al.'s (2003) qualitative study. Resick et al. (2006) also describe ethical leaders as people-oriented. The people orientation component in ethical leadership reflects genuinely caring about, respecting and supporting subordinates and where possible ensuring that their needs are met (Kanungo & Conger 1993; Treviño et al. 2003).
- **Ethical guidance:** it has been pinpointed that ethical leaders clearly convey standards regarding ethical conduct (Treviño et al. 2003). Organizations and top management set rules, standards and codes of conduct, which provide guidelines for ethical behavior (Beu &

Buckley 2001) and leaders can raise subordinates' awareness of such guidelines. Ethical leaders also use rewards and punishments to hold subordinates responsible for their actions (Treviño et al. 2003). According to Brown et al. (2005), ethical leaders guide followers in setting priorities and in ethical dilemmas they experience. We label this ethical guidance, which implies communication about ethics, explanation of ethical rules, and promotion and reward of ethical conduct among subordinates.

- **Fairness:** Kalshoven (2011) described fairness as an important form of ethical leader behavior and argued that ethical leaders act with integrity and treat others fairly. In furtherance, other scholars are not in dispute to the effect that ethical leaders make principled and fair choices; are trustworthy and honest, do not practice favoritism, and take responsibility for their own actions (Brown et al. 2005; De Hoogh & Den Hartog 2008; Treviño et al. 2003). In essence, this kind of leader would give every subordinate equal and deserving treatment in the affairs of the organization. He or she can be trusted for seeing everyone as equal members with applicable status in the organization as against treating some as being more equal than the others.
- **Integrity:** Integrity behaviors are described as word-deed alignment or the extent to which what one says is in line with what one does (e.g., Dineen, Lewicki, & Tomlinson, 2006; Palanski & Yammarino 2007, 2009). Leaders who keep promises and behave consistently can be trusted or believed because they work or behave as expected (Simons, 2002). Similarly, Yukl (2006) describes leaders as being ethical when they keep promises and behave consistently. Thus, ethical leaders keep their promises and act consistently, in a predictable way, which we label integrity (Kalshoven 2011).

Employee Engagement

Kahn (1990) coined one of the most recognizable definitions of engagement: “the harnessing of organizational members’ selves to their work role”. Work engagement is a state of enthusiastic and complete involvement in work (Rich et al. 2010; Cooper-Thomas et al. 2014). In furtherance, others have defined work engagement as “a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption” which can influence employee health (Schaufeli et al., 2006, Inoue et al. 2013); independent, persistent and pervasive motivational psychological state that accompanies the behavioral investment of personal energy (Schaufeli and Bakker 2010). And as a work-related construct that is multifaceted, and concerns employee emotional and intellectual commitment, involvement, passion for work, as well as a discretionary effort that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption while at work (Perryman and Hayday 2004; Schaufeli et al. 2002; Khan 1990). Common among these definitions are that engagement is a positive behavior, it is willfully exerted, related to work; involves vigorousness, dedication, and absorption, and more importantly, it contributes to organizational success.

Truss, Schantz, Soane, Alfes & Delbridge (2013) argued that William Khan was the first to introduce the concept of WE and that (Khan 1990) posited that employees use varying degree of their selves, physically, emotionally and cognitively in the work roles they perform. They further averred that employee engagement occurs when employees know what is expected of them, have what they need to do their work, have opportunities to feel an impact and fulfillment in their work, perceive that they are part of something significant with co-workers and have chances to improve and develop. Furthermore, there seem to be a consensus to the effect that employee engagement as a construct is built on the foundation of earlier concepts like satisfaction, job involvement and employee commitment (Hallberg and Schaufeli 2006; Robinson, Perryman and Hayday 2004; Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma and Bakker 2002). Accordingly, they maintain that EE is broader in scope. entails a two-way relationship between the employer and employee, has the potential to bring employers and employees closer to the benefit of both, affords employees the opportunity to experience a sense of oneness while at work, the space to express positive attitude

and be themselves, control or impact upon their environment and make positive contribution to the goals of the organization.

Measures of Employee Engagement

Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma and Bakker (2002) operationalised the construct of employee engagement as being characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption. They mentioned that engaged employees invest physical effort in their work, experience increased meaningfulness on their job and thus are more likely to be cognitively and emotionally attached to their work. This study adopts the three branches of employee engagement as discussed hereunder.

Vigor

Vigor refers to energy, mental resilience, and determination and investing consistent effort in job (Rayton and Yalabik 2014). Similarly, Macey & Schneider (2008), Schaufeli et al. (2002) described vigor as employee work situations that are characterized by high levels of physical, mental energies and resilience exerted on the job. Vigor is the willingness to invest effort in one's work and persistence when faced with difficulties at work. It is a positive state of mind exhibited by employees which propels them to selflessly take on more work, exert extra energy when confronted by challenges or work pressure in order to get work done. Employee vigor reflects a strong drive demonstrated through the exertion of energy, time spent and concentration on the job or activities related to the organization. Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) described vigor as the pace and focus which the employee brings into the job as a result of increased morale, motivation, sense of duty and connection to the goals of the organization. Employees who exhibit vigor at work are self driven, result focus, and determined to complete given tasks within the specified time frame.

Dedication

Dedication according to Rayton and Yalabik (2014) is about being inspired, enthusiastic and highly involved in your job. It is an individual's deriving a sense of significance from work, feeling enthusiastic and proud about the given job, and feeling inspired and challenged by the job (Song et al. 2012). According to Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) and Schaufeli et al. (2002), employee dedication reflects employees' sense of significance, passion, motivation and pride. Employees feel dedicated when they are inspired by challenges on the job. Dedication is about employees' persistence, consistency and continuity on the job aimed towards organizational goals. Employees' who display high levels of dedication are believed to be highly involved on their job roles and are seen to exert positive feelings towards the job and the organization. Dedication is synonymous to complete enmeshment into the blood veins of one's calling.

Absorption

Absorption points to a sense of detachment from one's surroundings, associated with a high degree of concentration on the job, and a general lack of conscious awareness of the amount of time spent on the job (Rayton and Yalabik 2014). On a similar note, absorption has been described as concentration and being engrossed in people's work, whereby passing time will be intangible and being detached from the job has some difficulties for them. This is characterized by being totally and happily immersed in one's work and having difficulty detaching oneself from it. It involves high levels of concentration, assimilation and embeddedness at work to the extent that one finds it difficult to separate from the work. Schaufeli et al. (2002) and Castellano (2015) noted that absorption has much to do with how much an employee is engrossed in a role and the intensity of his/her attention.

Ethical Leadership and Employee Engagement

Ethical leadership has been reported as having positive relationships with a variety of followers' attitudes, such as satisfaction with the leader, trust in management and perceived leader effectiveness

(e.g., Aronson 2001; Brown et al. 2005; Den Hartog & De Hoogh 2009; Kanungo 2001; Hartog & Belschak 2012) and specifically employee engagement (Kacmar et al. 2011; Sugianingrat, et al. 2017). Justifying this result, it was argued that employees, who feel supported, cared for and fairly treated are more likely to develop satisfaction and trust (cf., Brown et al. 2005; De Hoogh & Den Hartog 2008). In addition, Den Hartog and De Hoogh (2009) found a relationship between ethical leadership and commitment, and commitment is not too far from involvement, hence if ethical leadership can inspire commitment, it can also prompt involvement. When employees are treated in a fair and respectful way by their leaders, they are likely to think about their relationship with their leader in terms of social exchange (Blau 1964); rather than economic exchange.

Furthermore, they are likely to reciprocate by putting extra effort into their work, through enhanced job dedication (Brown et al. 2005) and willing to become more actively engaged in work (Macey et al., 2009). Ethical leaders take their followers into consideration and through open communication (Brown and Trevino 2006) clarify goals of the organisation's and what is expected from subordinates, which inspires employee engagement (Macey et al. 2009). Brown et al. (2005) found a positive correlation between ethical leadership and job dedication, which is a major element of work engagement (Schaufeli and Bakker 2003). In their study, using a regression analysis, Den Hartog and Belschak (2012) confirmed that ethical leadership has a positive relationship with work engagement. They found that followers tend to report higher engagement in their work when they perceive their leaders as acting ethically. Drawing from the foregoing, we are using four dimensions of ethical leadership and three measures of employee engagement to hypothesize as follows:

Figure 1. Operational Framework of Ethical Leadership and Job Involvement

H0₁: Ethical leadership is positively associated with job engagement of Police Officers in Port Harcourt.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted the descriptive method based on the relational screening model. Descriptive-relational screening studies according to Kaya, Balay & Gocen (2012) describe a situation or event as it is and show the relations between variables that caused the situation, their effects and rates.

Population

The population of this study comprises six hundred employees of five mobile telecommunication companies in Port Harcourt.

Sample Size

The sample size was two hundred and forty of employees of mobile telecommunication companies and was drawn through the Krejcie and Morgan Table of 1970.

Research Instrument and Procedures

In determining the ethical leadership scale (ELS), the study used four latent variables out of the total of seven that was developed by Kalshoven (2011) as dimensions of ethical leadership. The adopted four latent variables have a total of thirty instruments. For the dependent variable, three latent variables of vigor dedication and absorption were adopted. The work engagement scale of Shaufeli et al (2002a) with seventeen items was equally used.

Validity and Reliability

The questionnaire was construct and face validated by experts in ethical leadership and those in work engagement. The participants were also satisfied with the design of the questionnaire because they were simple and easy to answer to. On the other hand, reliability was calculated using the Cronbach's Alpha for each of the subset of the questions. The results showed satisfactory level of internal consistency.

Data Analysis

Data were first presented using tables and simple percentages and frequency tables. Subsequently, the hypotheses were tested using the T-Test and later the Multiple Regression Analysis was done to ascertain the association of dependent and independent variables.

Results. Questionnaire Administration

Table 1. Questionnaire Distribution

Name of Institutions	Population Size	Sample Size	No. Distributed	No. Not Returned	No. Returned	No. Discard	Useful Copies
Airtel Nigeria Limited	73	29	29	4	25	-	25
9Mobile Nigeria Limited	97	39	39	2	37	4	33
Globacom Telecommunications Limited	109	44	44	3	41	4	37
MTN Nigeria Limited	321	128	128	20	108	5	103
Grand Total	600	240	240(100)	29	211(88%)	13	198(82%)

Source: Survey Data 2019

Table 1 shows the copies of questionnaire distributed and retrieved, out of (240)100% copies sent out 211(88%) was retrieved, while 198(82%) was correctly filled and useful for the analysis.

Demographics Analysis of Respondent Profile. Age Bracket of Respondent

Table 2. Age Bracket of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Below 20 yrs	16	8.1	8.1	8.1
21-30 yrs	59	29.8	29.8	37.9
31-40 yrs	107	54.0	54.0	91.9
40 yrs and Above	16	8.1	8.1	100.0
Total	198	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output 2019

Table 2 showed that majority of the respondents, 107(54.0%) were within the age range of 31-40 years, 59(29.8%) were within 21-30 years. This shows that majority of the respondents are in their youthful years apparently follows a consistency between graduation and working experience, having the capability to give valid responses to our findings. While 16(8.1%) were within below 20 years and finally 16(8.1%) of the respondent were 40 years and above.

Marital Status of Respondent

Table 3. Marital Status of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Single	90	45.5	45.5	45.5
Married	108	54.5	54.5	100.0
Total	198	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output 2019

Table 3 revealed that 108(54.5%) of the respondents were married while 90(45.5%) were single, therefore, it observed that majority of the respondent are married people.

Sex of Respondents

Table 4. Gender of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	88	44.4	44.4	44.4
Female	110	55.6	55.6	100.0
Total	198	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output 2019

Table 4 above revealed that majority of the respondent are female 110 (55.6%) of the respondents were female while 88 (44.4%) are male.

Educational Qualification of Respondents

Table 5. Educational Qualification of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SSCE	14	7.1	7.1	7.1
B.Sc	102	51.5	51.5	58.6
P.G Degree	82	41.4	41.4	100.0
Total	198	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output 2019

The academic qualification of the respondents in Table 5 indicate that 14(7.1%) of the respondents had SSCE education, majority of the respondent had 102 (51.5%) Bachelor degree while 82 (41.4%) of the respondent had Post-Graduate Degree.

Working Experience of Respondents

Table 6. Years of Service of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Below 5 yrs	56	28.3	28.3	28.3
5-15 yrs	57	28.8	28.8	57.1
16-20 yrs	85	42.9	42.9	100.0
Total	198	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output 2019

The working experience of respondents understudy in Table 6 above indicates that respondents who had below 5 years working experience consist 56 (28.3%) of the responses drawn from this segment of the study, while 5-15 years working experience were 57 (28.8), while those that had 16-20 years and above working experience were 85 (42.9%) respectively. This show a high level experience of respondents used for this study.

Univariate Descriptive (Analyses of Research Questions)

The study adopted 5-Point Likert scale ranging from 5= Strongly Agree (SA), 4=Agree (A), 3 Neutral (N) 2= Disagree (D) 1= Strongly Disagree (SD) while the interpretation of the mean score and standard deviation is according to Asawo's (2009) categorization where all the responses with mean value (x) between 1.2 considered as low, 2.5-3.5 considered as moderate, 3.5–4.5 considered as high and 4.5 above considered as very high.

1. People Orientation as a Dimension of Ethical Leadership

The response rate of people orientation was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 7. Showed Descriptive Statistics on People Orientation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My boss is interested in how I feel and how I am doing	198	1	5	3.67	1.196
My boss takes time for personal contact	198	2	5	3.44	.915
My boss pays attention to my personal needs	198	1	4	2.89	1.082
Takes time to talk about work-related emotions	198	1	4	3.04	.889
My boss is genuinely concerned about my personal development	198	1	5	2.52	.877
My boss sympathizes with me when I have problems	198	1	5	3.57	.952
My boss cares about his/her followers	198	1	4	2.81	1.014
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 7 indicate the responses of respondents as it relates to people orientation with mean and standard deviation and scale in 7-item. All the items in the table above are considered as moderate. Item-1 in the table above shows respondent affirmed that their boss is interested in how they feel and how they are doing with a high mean score of ($x=3.67$). Followed by item-6 respondents affirmed that, there boss sympathizes with them when they have problems with high mean score of ($x=3.57$). Item-2 respondents affirmed that their boss takes time for personal contact with workers with moderate mean score of ($x=3.44$), followed by item-4 respondents also affirmed that their boss takes time to talk about work-related emotions with a moderate mean score of ($x=3.04$), other item in the table like item five, three and seven respectively respondents also affirmed that their boss pay attention and care for them in the organization with score of ($x= 2.89, 2.51$ and 2.81). The response rates show that their boss is considered moderately people oriented in the Telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt.

2. Ethical guidance as a dimension of ethical leadership

The response rate of ethical guidance was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 8. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Ethical Guidance

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My boss clearly explains integrity related codes of conduct	198	3	5	2.36	1.682
My boss explains what is expected from officers in terms of behaving with integrity	198	2	5	3.27	.724
My boss clarifies integrity guidelines	198	1	5	3.50	1.014
My boss ensures that employees follow codes of integrity	198	1	5	2.84	1.226
My boss clarifies the likely consequences of possible unethical behavior by myself and my colleagues	198	2	5	3.47	1.036
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 8 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to ethical guidance with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. All the items in the table above are considered as moderate. Item-3 in the table, respondent affirmed that their boss clarifies integrity guidelines with a moderate mean score of ($x=3.50$). Followed by item-2 respondents affirmed that their boss explains what is expected from officers in terms of behaving with integrity with a moderate mean score of ($x=3.27$). Item-5 respondents also affirmed that their boss clarifies the likely consequences of possible unethical behavior by myself and my colleagues with moderate mean score of ($x=3.47$), other item in the table like item 1 and 4 respectively respondents also affirmed that their boss clearly explains integrity related codes of conduct with mean score of ($x= 2.36$ and 2.84). The response rates show that their boss is considered moderately ethical oriented in the Telecommunication Companies in Port-Harcourt.

3. Fairness as a dimension of ethical leadership

The response rate of fairness was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 9. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Fairness

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My boss holds me accountable for problems over which I have no control	198	1	5	3.16	1.035
Holds me responsible for work that I gave no control over	198	3	5	3.67	.636
Holds me responsible for things that are not my fault	198	2	5	3.35	.809
Pursues his/her own success at the expense of others	198	3	5	3.79	.617
My boss is focused mainly on reaching his/her own goals	198	1	5	2.96	1.004
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 9 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to fairness with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. All the items in the table above are considered as moderate. Item-4 in the table, respondent affirmed that their boss Pursues his/her own success at the expense of others with a high mean score of ($x=3.79$). Followed by item-2 respondents affirmed that their boss Holds me responsible for work that I gave no control over with a high mean score of ($x=3.67$). Item-3 respondents also affirmed that their boss Holds me responsible for things that are not my fault with moderate mean score of ($x=3.35$), other item in the table like item-5 and 1 respectively respondents also affirmed that their boss is focused mainly on reaching his/her own goals with a moderate mean score of ($x= 2.96$ and 3.16). The response rates show that their boss is considered high and moderately fair to the workers in the Telecommunication Companies in Port-Harcourt.

4. Integrity as a dimension of ethical leadership

The response rate of integrity was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 10. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Integrity

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My boss keep to his/her promises	198	1	5	4.12	.904
My boss can be trusted to do the things he/she says	198	1	5	3.06	.899
My boss can be relied on to honour his/her commitments	198	1	5	3.21	1.236
My boss always keeps his/her words	198	1	5	2.44	1.272
Stakeholders developed a strong confidence on my organization.	198	3	5	3.83	.720
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 10 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to integrity with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. All the items in the table above are considered as moderate. Item-1 in the table, respondent affirmed that their boss keep to his/her promises with a high mean score of ($x=4.12$). Followed by item-5 respondents affirmed that Stakeholders developed a strong confidence on the organization with a high mean score of ($x=3.83$). Item-3 respondents also

affirmed that their boss can be relied on to honors his/her commitments with a moderate mean score of ($x=3.21$), other item in the table like item-4 and 2 respectively respondents also affirmed that their boss always keeps his/her words with a moderate mean score of ($x= 2.44$ and 3.06). The response rates show that their boss is considered high and moderately integrity to his words in the Telecommunication Companies in Port-Harcourt.

Measures of work engagement

1. Vigor as a Measure of work engagement

The response rate of vigor was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 11. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Vigor

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
At my work I feel strong and vigorous	198	1	5	2.64	1.477
When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work always	198	1	5	3.09	1.390
I can continue working for very long periods of a time	198	1	5	3.02	.945
At my work, I am very resilient, mentally	198	2	5	4.07	.846
At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well.	198	1	5	2.99	1.294
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 11 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to vigor with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. Respondent are in agreement that at their work, they are very resilient and mentally with a high mean score of ($x- 4.07$). Responses on the 2-item also affirmed that when they got up in the morning, they feel like going to work at a time with a moderate mean score of ($x-3.09$). The respondents on the 3-item affirmed that they can work for very long periods of a time with a moderate mean score of ($x-3.02$). Item 5 and 1 respondent also indicate a moderate mean score of ($x-2.99$ and 2.64) respectively. Therefore all the items in the table above are considered as moderate in the Telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt.

2. Dedication as a measure of ethical leadership

The response rate of dedication was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 12. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Dedication

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	198	1	5	3.42	.972
I am enthusiastic about my job.	198	1	5	2.68	1.289
My job inspires me	198	2	5	3.76	.714
I am proud of the work that I do	198	1	5	2.31	1.105
To me, my job is challenging	198	1	5	3.48	.986
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Table 12 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to dedication with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. Respondents of 3th-item confirmed that their job inspires them with a high mean score of (x- 3.76). Responses on the 5th-item also affirmed that their job is challenging with a moderate mean score of (x-3.48). The respondents on the 1st-item affirmed that they find the work they do with full of meaning and purpose with a moderate mean score of (x-3.42). The 2nd and 4th Item in the table above respondent also confirmed with a moderate mean score of (x-2.68 and 2.31) respectively. Therefore all the items in the table above are considered as moderate in the Telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt.

3. Absorption as a measure of ethical leadership

The response rate of absorption was analyzed using descriptive statistics indicating mean and standard deviation.

Table 13. Showed Descriptive Statistics on Absorption

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Time flies when I am working	198	1	5	2.73	1.034
When I am working, I forget everything else around me	198	1	5	3.41	1.113
I feel happy when I am working intensely	198	2	5	3.50	.828
I am immersed in my work	198	2	5	3.13	1.091
I get carried away when I am working	198	1	5	2.99	1.230
Valid N (listwise)	198				

Source: (SPSS 22) Output, 2019

Table 13 indicate the responses of respondents as it relate to absorption with mean and standard deviation and scale in 5-Item. Respondents of the 3th-item confirmed that they feel happy when they are working intensely with a moderate mean score of (x- 3.50). Responses on the 4th-item also affirmed that they am immersed in their work with a moderate mean score of (x-3.13). The respondents on the 2nd-item affirmed that when they are working, they forget everything else around them with a moderate mean score of (x-3.41). The 5th and 1st Item in the table above respondent also confirmed with a moderate mean score of (x-2.99 and 2.73) respectively. Therefore all the items in the table above are considered as moderate in the Telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt.

Regression Analysis (Test of Hypotheses)

The multiple-regression analysis was used to empirically test the twelve hypotheses on whether to reject or accept the null hypotheses. The basics were to establish the association between the predictor variables and the criterion variables. The hypotheses were tested at 95% level of confidence in order to draw conclusion.

Model 1 Showed the Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness and Integrity) on Vigor.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.789 ^a	.778	.748	.660

a. Predictors: (Constant), Integrity, Fairness, Ethical guidance, People orientation

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Model 1, above showed the result of regression analysis (R-value 0.789) between the criterion variable (**vigor**) and the predictor variable of Ethical Leadership (**people orientation, ethical guidance, fairness and integrity**) that taken together. The (R-value =0.789) indicates that the predictor variables had a strong association with the criterion variable. The coefficient of determination (R^2 -value 0.778) implies that both predictor variables explain 77.8% variance of **vigor** while remaining 22.2% could be due to the effect of extraneous variables.

Table 14. Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness, Integrity) and Vigor

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.251	.458		-7.096	.000
	People orientation	.916	.069	1.042	13.185	.000
	Ethical guidance	-.345	.090	-.265	-3.826	.000
	Fairness	.213	.076	.142	2.783	.006
	Integrity	.084	.075	.069	1.121	.264

a. Dependent Variable: Vigor

Source: (SPSS 22) Output 2019

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between people orientation and vigor in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 14 above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between people orientation and vigor is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 13.185) at significant level of (P=0.000) at 95% level of confidence and (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal=13.185 with (P>.000) indicates that there is a strong positive and significant relationship between people orientation and vigor. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly people orientation as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.916$) to the variation of the criterion variable (vigor). This means that people orientation makes a strong and unique contribution to explain the variation in criterion variable (vigor).

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between ethical guidance and vigor in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.18b above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between ethical guidance and vigor is statistically negative and significant with a (t-statistic value of -3.826) at significant level of (P=0.000) at 95% level of confidence and (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= -3.826 with (P>.000) indicates that there is a negative and significant relationship between ethical guidance and vigor. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly ethical guidance as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta= -0.345$) to the variation of the criterion variable (vigor). This means that ethical guidance makes a unique contribution to explain the variation in criterion variable (vigor).

Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between fairness and vigor in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.18c above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between fairness and vigor is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 2.723) at significant level

of (P=0.006) at 95% level of confidence and (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 2.723 with (P>.000) indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between fairness and vigor. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly fairness as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta = -0.345$) to the variation of the criterion variable (vigor). This means that fairness makes a unique contribution to explain the variation in criterion variable (vigor).

Hypothesis 4

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between integrity and vigor in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.18d above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between integrity and vigor is not statistically significant with a (t-statistic value of 1.121) at significant level of (P=0.264) at 95% level of confidence and (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 1.121 with (P>.264) indicates that there is no significant relationship between integrity and vigor. **Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly integrity as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta = 0.084$) to the variation of the criterion variable (vigor). This means that integrity makes a low contribution to explain the variation in criterion variable (vigor).

Model 2 Showed the Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness and Integrity) on Dedication.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.688 ^a	.676	.675	.554

a. Predictors: (Constant), Integrity, Fairness, Ethical guidance, People orientation

Source: (SPSS 22) Output, 2019

Model 2, above showed the result of regression analysis (R-value 0.688) between the criterion variable (**dedication**) and the predictor variable of Ethical Leadership (**people orientation, ethical guidance, fairness and integrity**) that taken together. The (R-value =0.688) indicates that the predictor variables had a strong effect on the criterion variable. The coefficient of determination (R²-value 0.676) implies that both predictor variables explain 67.6% variance of **dedication** while remaining 32.4% could be due to the effect of extraneous variables.

Table 15. Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness, Integrity) and Dedication

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.448	.402		-8.584	.000
	People orientation	.090	.061	.124	1.483	.140
	Ethical guidance	.057	.079	.052	.716	.475
	Fairness	.658	.067	.527	9.825	.000
	Integrity	.299	.066	.294	4.525	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Dedication

Source: (SPSS 22) Output, 2019

Hypothesis 5

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between people orientation and dedication in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.19a above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between people orientation and dedication is not statistically significant with a (t-statistic value of 1.483) at significant level of (P=0.140) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 1.483 with (P>0.140) indicates that there is no significant relationship between people orientation and dedication. **Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly people orientation as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.090$) to the variation of the criterion variable (dedication). This means that people orientation makes a low contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (dedication).

Hypothesis 6

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between ethical guidance and dedication in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.19b above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between ethical guidance and dedication is not statistically significant with a (t-statistic value of 0.716) at significant level of (P=0.475) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 0.716 with (P>0.475) indicates that there is no significant relationship between ethical guidance and dedication. **Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly ethical guidance as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.057$) to the variation of the criterion variable (dedication). This means that ethical guidance makes a low contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (dedication).

Hypothesis 7

H₀₇: There is no significant relationship between fairness and dedication in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.19c above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between fairness and dedication is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 9.825) at significant level of (P=0.000) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 9.825 with (P>0.000) indicates that there is a statistical positive and significant relationship between fairness and dedication. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly fairness as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.658$) to the variation of the criterion variable (dedication). This means that fairness makes a unique contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (dedication).

Hypothesis 8

H₀₈: There is no significant relationship between integrity and dedication in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.19d above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between integrity and dedication is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 4.525) at significant level of (P=0.000) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 4.525 with (P>0.000) indicates that there is a statistical positive and significant relationship between integrity and dedication. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly integrity as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.299$) to the variation of the criterion variable (dedication). This means that integrity makes a unique contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (dedication).

Model 3 Showed the Effect of Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness and Integrity) on Absorption

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.788 ^a	.775	.725	.601

a. Predictors: (Constant), Integrity, Fairness, Ethical guidance, People orientation

Source: (SPSS 22) Output, 2019

Model 3, above showed the result of regression analysis (R-value 0.788) between the criterion variable (**absorption**) and the predictor variable Nexus of Ethical Leadership (**people orientation, ethical guidance, fairness and integrity**) that taken together. The (R-value =0.788) indicates that the predictor variables had a strong effect on the criterion variable. The coefficient of determination (R²-value 0.775) implies that both predictor variables explain 77.5% variance of **absorption** while the remaining 22.5% could be due to the effect of extraneous variables.

Table 16. Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Nexus of Ethical Leadership (People Orientation, Ethical Guidance, Fairness, Integrity) and Absorption

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.546	.427		-5.965	.000
	People orientation	.493	.065	.643	7.625	.000
	Ethical guidance	.492	.084	.432	5.867	.000
	Fairness	.035	.071	.332	1.117	.432
	Integrity	-.447	.070	-.419	-6.378	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Absorption

Source: (SPSS 22) Output, 2019

Hypothesis 9

H₀₉: There is no significant relationship between people orientation and absorption in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.20a above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between people orientation and absorption is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 7.625) at significant level of (P=0.000) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 7.625 with (P>0.000) indicates that there is a statistical positive and significant relationship between people orientation and absorption. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly people orientation as a predictor variable contributes (β=0.493) to the variation of the criterion variable (absorption). This means that people orientation makes a unique contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (absorption).

Hypothesis 10

H₀₁₀: There is no significant relationship between ethical guidance and absorption in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.20b above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between ethical guidance and absorption is statistically positive and significant with a (t-statistic value of 5.867) at significant level of (P=0.000) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 5.867 with (P>0.000) indicates that there is a statistical positive and significant relationship between ethical

guidance and absorption. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly ethical guidance as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.492$) to the variation of the criterion variable (absorption). This means that ethical guidance makes a unique contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (absorption).

Hypothesis 11

H₀₁₁: There is no significant relationship between fairness and absorption in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.20c above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between fairness and absorption is no statistically significant with a (t-statistic value of 1.117) at significant level of ($P=0.432$) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= 1.117 with ($P>0.432$) indicates that there is no significant relationship between fairness and absorption. **Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly fairness as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta=0.035$) to the variation of the criterion variable (absorption). This means that fairness makes a low contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (absorption).

Hypothesis 12

H₀₁₂: There is no significant relationship between integrity and absorption in the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4.20d above indicates the result of correlation coefficient. The relationship between integrity and absorption is statistically negative and significant with a (t-statistic value of -6.378) at significant level of ($P=0.000$) and 95% level of confidence, (t-crit =1.96). The t-cal= -6.378 with ($P>0.000$) indicates that there is a statistical negative and significant relationship between integrity and absorption. **Thus, the alternate hypothesis is hereby accepted.** Similarly integrity as a predictor variable contributes ($\beta= -0.447$) to the variation of the criterion variable (absorption). This means that integrity makes a unique contribution to explain the variation of the criterion variable (absorption).

Discussion

Ethical leadership was found to be positively associated with employees' work engagement as all the dimensions of ethical leadership were associated with the measures of employee engagement and this result reflects similar findings where ethical leadership was found as having positive relationships with a variety of followers' attitudes, such as satisfaction with the leader, trust in management and perceived leader effectiveness (e.g., Aronson 2001; Brown et al., 2005; Den Hartog & De Hoogh 2009; Kanungo 2001; Hartog & Belschak 2012) and specifically employee engagement (Kacmar et al. 2011; Sugianingrat, et al, 2017). Justifying this result, it was argued that employees, who feel supported, cared for and fairly treated are more likely to develop satisfaction and trust (cf., Brown et al.,2005; De Hoogh & Den Hartog 2008). In addition, Den Hartog and De Hoogh (2009) found a relationship between ethical leadership and commitment, and commitment is not too far from involvement, hence if ethical leadership can inspire commitment, it can also prompt involvement. When employees are treated in a fair and respectful way by their leaders, they are likely to think about their relationship with their leader in terms of social exchange (Blau, 1964); rather than economic exchange.

Furthermore, they are likely to reciprocate by putting extra effort into their work, through enhanced job dedication (Brown et al., 2005) and willing to become more actively engaged in work (Macey et al. 2009). Ethical leaders take their followers into consideration and through open communication (Brown and Trevino 2006) clarify goals of the organisation's and what is expected from subordinates, which inspires employee engagement (Macey et al. 2009). Brown et al. (2005) found a positive correlation between ethical leadership and job dedication, which is a major element of work engagement (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2003). In their study, using a regression analysis, Den Hartog and Belschak (2012) confirmed that ethical leadership has a positive relationship with work

engagement. They found that followers tend to report higher engagement in their work when they perceive their leaders as acting ethically. Drawing from the foregoing, we are using four dimensions of ethical leadership and three measures of employee engagement to hypothesize as follows:

Summary

1. People orientation is positively associated with work engagement of the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.
2. Ethical guidance is positively associated with work engagement of the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.
3. Fairness is positively associated with work engagement of the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.
4. Integrity is positively associated with work engagement of the telecommunication companies in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Conclusion

Ethical mindfulness is incontrovertibly a sine qua none characteristics of every leadership style, but ethical leadership itself has come to stay and is speedily gaining scholarly attention across leadership literature. The bequeathing of ethical leadership on followers is a great way to demonstrate leadership by example. When leadership is approached from these ethical dimensions, it will result in an increase in the employee's sense of control, broaden an individual's responsibilities, and create a sense of psychological meaningfulness, thus inducing greater motivation and increased effort by employees (Piccolo et al. 2010). In fact, ethical leadership is not only good for the leaders' reputation, but is also a contagious practice that is capable of stimulating positive workplace value and practices among workers. Similarly, having employees who are engaged in their work would contribute in no small measures to the overall performance of the organization; hence the overarching value of ethical leadership in today's organization.

Recommendations

Going by the findings of this study, the following are our recommendations

1. Leadership should be people oriented in administering the enterprise so that employees can be stimulated towards being dedicated, showing vigor and being absorbed at work.
2. Leaders should provide ethical guidance to their subordinates and in so doing; such subordinates will also learn and extend such attitude in delivering their jobs.
3. Leaders should be fair to all and sundry by avoiding favoritism, nepotism, and other biased judgments in dealing with subordinates so that they can be trusted and willingly obeyed which can culminate in work engagement.
4. Leaders should have great concern for their personal integrity because they are the immediate role models of their subordinates who would like to do as their leaders do.

References

- Aronson, E. 2001. "Integrating leadership styles and ethical perspectives." *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences* 18: 244–256.
- Bakker, A.B., Demerouti, E. & Ten Brummelhuis, L.L. 2012. "Work engagement, performance and active learning : the role of conscientiousness." *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 80 (2): 555-564.
- Bandura, A. 1986. *Social foundation of thought and action. Englewood Cliffs*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Blau, P. 1964. *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: Wiley & Sons.
- Brown, M.E., & Treviño, L.K. 2006. "Ethical leadership: A review and future directions." *Leadership Quarterly* 17: 595-616.
- Brown, M.E., Treviño, L.K., & Harrison, D.A. 2005. "Ethical leadership: A social learning perspective for construct development and testing." *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 97: 117–134.
- Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A.A., & Toth, P. 1997. "The relationship of organizational politics and support to work behaviors, attitudes, and stress." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 18: 159–180.

- De Hoogh, A. H. B., & Den Hartog, D. N. 2008. "Ethical and despotic leadership, relationships with leader's social responsibility, top management team effectiveness and subordinates' optimism: A multi-method study". *Leadership Quarterly* 19: 297–311.
- De Hoogh, A. H. B., & Den Hartog, D. N. 2009. "Ethical leadership: The positive and responsible use of power." In D. Tjsovold, & B. Van Knippenberg (Eds.), *Power and interdependence in organizations*.
- Den Hartog, D. N., & De Hoogh 2009. "Empowerment and leader fairness and integrity: Studying ethical leader behavior: From a levels-of-analysis perspective." *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* 18: 199–230.
- Dineen, B. R., Lewicki, R. J., & Tomlinson, E. C. 2006. "Supervisory guidance and behavioral integrity: Relationships with employee citizenship and deviant behavior." *The Journal of Applied Psychology* 91: 622–635.
- Eisenbeiss, S.A. 2012. "Re-thinking ethical leadership: An interdisciplinary integrative approach." *The Leadership Quarterly* (23): 791–808.
- Emerson, R. 1972. "Power-dependence relations." *American Sociological Review* 27(1): 31- 41.
- Engelbrecht, A.S., Heine, G. and Mahembe, B. 2017. "Integrity, ethical leadership, trust and work engagement." *Leadership & Organization Development Journal* 38(3):368-379.
- Harter, J. K., Schmidt, F. L., & Hayes, T. L. 2002. "Business-unit-level relationship between employee satisfaction, employee engagement, and business outcomes: A meta-analysis." *Journal of Applied Psychology* (87): 268–279.
- Homans, G. C. 1958. "Social behavior as exchange." *American Journal of Sociology* 63: 597–606.
- Kahn, W.A. 1990. "Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work." *Academy of Management Journal* 33 (4): 692-724.
- Kalshoven, K., Den Hartog, D. N., & De Hoogh, A. H. B. 2010. "Ethical leader behavior and big five factors of personality." *Journal of Business Ethics* 100(2): 349-366.
- Kalshoven, K., Den Hartog, D. N., & De Hoogh, A. H. B. 2011. "Ethical leadership at work questionnaire (ELW): Development and validation of a multidimensional measure." *The Leadership Quarterly* 22(1): 51-69.
- Kanungo, R. N., & Mendonca, M. 1996. *Ethical dimensions of leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Kanungo, R.N. 2001. "Ethical values of transactional and transformational leaders." *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences* 18(4): 257-265.
- Macey, W.H., Schneider, B., Barbera, K.M. and Young, S.A. 2009. *Employee Engagement: Tools for Analysis, Practice and Competitive Advantage*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Resick, C.J., Hanges, P.J., Dickson, M.W. & Mitchelson, J.K. 2006. "A cross-cultural examination of the endorsement of ethical leadership." *Journal of Business Ethics* 63 (4): 345-359.
- Robinson, D. Perryman S. and Hayday, S. 2004. "The drivers of employee engagement." Institute for Employment Studies.
- Sabir, M.S., Iqbal, J.J., Rehman, K.U., Shah, K.A., Yameen, M. 2012. "Impact of corporate ethical values on ethical leadership and employee performance." *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 3 (2): 163-171.
- Saks, A. 2006. "Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement." *Journal of Psychology Management (n.v & s)*: 600-618. Retrieved Sunday 10th September, 2018 from www.emeraldinsights.com/0268-3946.htm.
- Schaufeli, W. and Bakker, A. 2003. *Utrecht work engagement scale preliminary manual, occupational health psychology unit*. Utrecht: Utrecht University.
- Shaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., Gonzalez-Roma, V. & Bakker, A. B. 2002a. "The measurement of engagement and burnout and: A confirmative analytic approach." *Journal of Happiness Studies* 3: 71-92.
- Simons, T. 2002. "Behavioural integrity: the perceived alignment between managers' word and deeds as a research focus." *Organizational Science* 13 (1): 18-35.
- Sugianingrat, I.A.P.W., Yasa, N.Y.K., Sintaasih, D.K., Subudi, M. 2017. "The influence of ethical leadership on employee performance through employee engagement." *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 22(12): 4-11.
- Tims, M., Bakker, A.B. and Xanthopoulou, D. 2011. "Do transformational leaders enhance their followers' daily work engagement?" *The Leadership Quarterly* 22 (1): 121-131.
- Treviño, L. K., Hartman, L. P., & Brown, M. 2000. "Moral person and moral manager: How executives develop a reputation for ethical leadership." *California Management Review* 42: 128–142.
- Turner, B. L., Kasperson, R. E., Matsone, P. A., McCarthy, J. J., Corellg, R. W., Christensene, L., Eckley, N., Kasperson, J. X., Luers, A., Martello, M. L., Polsky, C., Pulsipher, A., & Schiller, A. 2003. "A framework for vulnerability analysis in sustainability science." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* 100(14): 8074-8079.
- Turner, N., Barling, J., Epitropaki, O., Butcher, V., & Milder, C. 2002. "Transformational leadership and moral reasoning." *The Journal of Applied Psychology* 87: 304–311.
- Walumbwa, F. O., Schaubroeck, J. 2009. "Leader personality traits and employee voice behavior: Mediating roles of ethical leadership and work group psychological safety." *Journal of Applied Psychology* 94 (5):1275-1286.
- Yukl, G., Mahsud, R., Hassan, S. and Prussia, G.E. 2011. "An improved measure of ethical leadership." *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies* 20 (10): 1-11.
- Zehir, E.Cemal,B & Erdogan, K. 2011. "The association between organizational silence and ethical leadership through employee performance." *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 24 (2): 1389-1404.